

Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Zanini, M. T., Salles, A., & Kock, N. (2025). Fostering public sector innovation: How data-driven organizational culture influences exploitation innovations. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*, 29(4), e240179. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-7849rac2025240179.en>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Zanini, M. T., Salles, A., Kock, N., & Ávila, T. (2025). Peer review report for: Fostering public sector innovation: How data-driven organizational culture influences exploitation innovations. RAC. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16277645>

REVIEWERS:

- Thiago Ávila (Fundação Getulio Vargas, Brazil)
The others reviewers did not authorize the disclosure of their report.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Thiago Ávila
Date review returned: November 18, 2024
Recommendation: Minor revision

Comments to the authors

First, I want to congratulate the author on this research proposal. It is exciting that this kind of research brings new capabilities, technologies, and methods to improve public institutions' innovation and routines and public servants' capabilities and literacy.

I have worked several times with Digital Government and Business Intelligence and Analytics in my academic and professional career. For this reason, I accept the invitation to review your paper.

In the abstract, you highlight the study's theoretical approach to IS and KM theories. What theories? I suggest you be more precise, bringing up the main theories supporting your research.

In the introduction, I observed some unnecessary phrases that bring a conversational approach to your paper—for example, comparing the data with the lifeblood of daily operations. I strongly disagree with this affirmative. Data is growing exponentially in importance in institutions, but it is not enough to be compared with a lifeblood.

You bring a typical discussion about the "data is the new oil" to your paper. On one side, some papers and opinion articles discuss this affirmative, but there are other papers and opinion articles that disagree with this affirmative [1, 2]. I want to suggest a quick reflection: "What kind of benefits does this kind of association aggregate to your research"?

[1] Ankerstjerne, 2009. Workplace-11-2019-02E.pdf

[2] Scholz, 2019. Big Data Is Not Big Oil: The Role of Analogy in the Law of New Technologies. Available in Big Data Is Not Big Oil: The Role of Analogy in the Law of New Technologies 86 Tennessee Law Review 2018-2019

In another paragraph, you bring another affirmative comparing the capacity of developing and exploiting innovations in the public and private sectors. Again, I suggest the same quick reflection for this association.

Exploring your model, I have two observations.

1. In section 4, when you describe the results of Table 4, you don't mention whether removing some variables was necessary until the convergent and divergent validity is obtained. Reading the text, the reader has the impression that the PLS procedure was a perfect success. I suggest that you explain the composition of Table 4 better.

2. Why didn't you use a variable to control the professional skills of the respondents?

For example, if your sample has a majority of professionals with a background in STEM, won't this background cause bias in your study? Could it be replicated in an institution where the professional profile is mainly made up of people with a background in social sciences without advanced literacy in the use of data, for example?

3. I want access to your database to better assess the effectiveness of your model. I suggest you make the database available so your study can be replicated and validated.

I hope my contributions will improve your paper. I made this review in Nov 2024

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: No

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state "none" if this is not applicable): none

Rating:

Interest: 2. Good

Quality: 2. Good

Originality: 2. Good

Overall: 2. Good

Authors' Responses

Comments:

Reviewer: 1

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 1 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report

Comments:

Reviewer: 2

Comments:

First, I want to congratulate the author on this research proposal. It is exciting that this kind of research brings new capabilities, technologies, and methods to improve public institutions' innovation and routines and public servants' capabilities and literacy. I have worked several times with Digital Government and Business Intelligence and Analytics in my academic and professional career. For this reason, I accept the invitation to review your paper. In the abstract, you highlight the study's theoretical approach to IS and KM theories. What theories? I suggest you be more precise, bringing up the main theories supporting your research.

Authors' response: We refer to Information Systems and Knowledge Management theories to investigate the interplay between organizational culture, business analytics capabilities, knowledge management, and information systems. Specifically, we draw on theories to understand how individuals adopt and use business analytics tools, and to examine the role of social relationships in knowledge sharing and collaboration.

In the introduction, I observed some unnecessary phrases that bring a conversational approach to your paper—for example, comparing the data with the lifeblood of daily operations. I strongly disagree with this affirmative. Data is growing exponentially in importance in institutions, but it is not enough to be compared with a lifeblood.

You bring a typical discussion about the "data is the new oil" to your paper. On one side, some papers and opinion articles discuss this affirmative, but there are other papers and opinion articles that disagree with this affirmative [1, 2]. I want to suggest a quick reflection: "What kind of benefits does this kind of association aggregate to your research"?

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In another paragraph, you bring another affirmative comparing the capacity of developing and exploiting innovations in the public and private sectors. Again, I suggest the same quick reflection for this association.

Authors' response: We now eliminated these unnecessary phrases in this revised version of our paper.

Exploring your model, I have two observations.

1. In section 4, when you describe the results of Table 4, you don't mention whether removing some variables was necessary until the convergent and divergent validity is obtained. Reading the text, the reader has the impression that the PLS procedure was a perfect success. I suggest that you explain the composition of Table 4 better.

Authors' response: Thank you for this very insightful comment. We now state at the top of the "Measurement model assessment" section that our use of the first-second order LV scheme was not only suggested by our theoretical development, but also

provided the basis for fairly good validity and reliability results. We also acknowledge this insightful note by the expert reviewer; indeed, our measurement model assessment results would not have been as good without the first-second order LV scheme we employed.

2. Why didn't you use a variable to control the professional skills of the respondents? For example, if your sample has a majority of professionals with a background in STEM, won't this background cause bias in your study? Could it be replicated in an institution where the professional profile is mainly made up of people with a background in social sciences without advanced literacy in the use of data, for example?

Authors' response: This is a very good point, which we addressed through a revision of the section "Limitations and future research". We now state that a particularly noteworthy limitation of our study is the fact the participants were quite well educated and likely proficient with the use of data for decision making: officers with the ranks of Lieutenant Commander (LC) and Commander (CC) in administrative functions in the Brazilian Navy. We now point out that future studies should include samples of professionals with different profiles; e.g., individuals with backgrounds more focused on the social sciences and without advanced literacy in the use of data.

3. I want access to your database to better assess the effectiveness of your model. I suggest you make the database available so your study can be replicated and validated.

I hope my contributions will improve your paper. I made this review in Nov 2024.

Authors' response: We thank you for your valuable comments.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Responses

Reviewer: 1

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 1 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

Reviewer: 2

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

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